

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF RENAL BLOOD FLOW PARAMETERS IN PREGNANCY COMPLICATED BY PREECLAMPSIA

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Abstract

The study evaluated renal blood flow parameters in pregnant women with moderate and severe preeclampsia using Dopplerography. A total of 42 pregnant women were examined. The results showed significant impairment of renal hemodynamics, especially in severe preeclampsia, with increased SDR and RI values. These changes reflected vascular spasm and endothelial dysfunction associated with disease severity. Renal artery Dopplerography was found to be a reliable and informative method for assessing renal blood flow in preeclampsia.

Keywords

preeclampsia, pregnancy, renal blood flow, Dopplerography, renal hemodynamics, resistance index.

Relevance

Preeclampsia, which poses a serious threat to maternal and infant health, is currently observed in 5–10% of pregnant women, and this rate continues to increase. The main mechanism of the disease is associated with vasoconstriction and damage to the inner vascular wall, which disrupts blood circulation in all organs. In this process, the kidneys are among the most affected organs. Due to swelling and narrowing of the renal capillaries, blood flow and filtration sharply decrease. Therefore, studying the renal blood circulation system is very important for determining the severity of preeclampsia and preventing dangerous complications.

Purpose of the study

To conduct a comparative analysis of changes in the renal blood flow system in pregnant women with moderate and severe forms of preeclampsia based on Dopplerometric criteria.

Materials and methods

A total of 42 pregnant women complicated by preeclampsia (aged 18–35 years, mean age: 27.3 ± 3.8 years) were examined. Exclusion criteria included chronic kidney diseases, pregestational hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and multiple pregnancy. Based on clinical signs, proteinuria, and blood pressure levels, patients were divided into groups with moderate preeclampsia (Group I, $n=24$) and severe preeclampsia (Group II, $n=18$).

Results

Renal hemodynamic parameters (SDR and RI) were assessed using an expert-class ultrasound machine with Dopplerographic visualization of the main and segmental arteries. The average value of each parameter was obtained from triple measurements. Biostatistical analysis was performed using the “Statistica 10.0” software package, and intergroup differences were evaluated using Student’s t-test ($p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant). Doppler examination showed impaired renal hemodynamics in women with preeclampsia. In moderate preeclampsia, vascular resistance was moderately increased (SDR 2.39 ± 0.10 ; RI 0.60 ± 0.03), whereas in severe preeclampsia the changes were more pronounced (SDR 2.67 ± 0.12 ; RI 0.64 ± 0.04 ; $p < 0.05$). In 72% of women with severe preeclampsia, the RI exceeded 0.62.

Discussion

Increased SDR and RI reflect vascular spasm and elevated peripheral resistance associated with endothelial dysfunction. The severity of hemodynamic disturbances is closely related to the severity of preeclampsia. Dopplerography of the renal arteries is a

non-invasive and reliable method important for assessing disease severity and determining the timing of delivery.

Conclusion

In pregnant women with preeclampsia, a statistically significant increase in vascular resistance in the renal arteries was observed, indicating impaired renal hemodynamics. In moderate preeclampsia, SDR and RI increased moderately, while severe preeclampsia was accompanied by pronounced disturbances — these indicators were significantly higher compared to normal values and the moderate preeclampsia group. Therefore, Dopplerography of the renal arteries is an informative and reliable method for assessing renal blood flow in preeclampsia and should be included in the комплекс monitoring system for these patients.

Referens

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